

Field Trial Validation of 5G-Connected UAVs towards QoS and Handover Analysis

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Abstract—As Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) become increasingly integrated into various commercial and public applications, ensuring reliable and high-quality connectivity is paramount, particularly in Beyond-Line-of-Sight (BLOS) scenarios. With a special focus on 5G cellular technology, this paper addresses the unique challenges posed by UAVs in cellular networks, such as rapid mobility and high-altitude signal degradation, through a comprehensive analysis of field trials conducted on a commercial 5G network. These trials aim to validate the performance of cellular connected UAVs by examining how handovers impact Quality of Service (QoS). The focus is on understanding the link between handover processes and the overall QoS experienced by the UAVs. Through dedicated field trials, we assessed QoS performance metrics, including latency, throughput, and signal strength continuity. The results reveal a correlation between QoS and handover performance, highlighting the potential of advanced handover strategies to enhance the deployment of UAVs in cellular networks.

Keywords—UAV, QoS, handover, latency, throughput, trials, 5G.

I. INTRODUCTION

The progress of UxV (Unmanned x Vehicle) related technology, particularly Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) also known as drones, opens the possibility for more versatile solutions and offers significant contributions to the challenges emerging in cellular 5G and B5G networks. These devices, which do not require human operators, possess many merits: drones can function as isolated mobile nodes or as part of an opportunistic network, which may consist of a swarm of homogeneous or heterogeneous mobile devices (nodes). They can be rapidly deployed at low cost, anytime and anywhere, with highly configurable characteristics. Specifically, the number of deployed drones (affecting the swarm network nodal density) and their degree and pattern of mobility can be tailored, allowing the network to scale up to achieve a target communication potential. On the other hand, leveraging cellular connectivity enables UAVs to transmit data in real time, receive commands remotely, and maintain continuous communication with ground stations or control centres.

However, integrating UAVs with cellular networks involves addressing key aspects such as Quality of Service (QoS) performance and handover efficiency, especially when UAV Command and Control (C2) are delivered over a 5G cellular network. As UAVs traverse vast geographical areas and rapidly change altitude, they encounter fluctuating signal strengths and latency issues. Therefore, effectively managing these factors is essential for unlocking the full potential of UAV applications across various sectors. While sufficient for many UAV applications, cellular networks were not initially designed for aerial vehicles mainly for two reasons. Firstly, coverage and signal strength are optimized for ground-level users. Cellular networks primarily aim to provide strong and reliable signals to mobile phones and handheld devices used on the ground. The antennas and base stations are oriented and configured to maximize coverage at ground level, not at the higher altitudes where aerial vehicles typically operate. Secondly, the mobility and speed of aerial vehicles present distinct considerations. Drones and other aerial vehicles move at higher speeds and along complex trajectories in three-dimensional space, unlike ground vehicles that move on relatively flat terrain. This rapid and varied movement can lead to frequent handovers between cells, which traditional cellular networks may not handle efficiently, causing potential connectivity issues.

This has led to several challenges that are being progressively addressed, and indeed standardisation endeavours such as in 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Release 17, Rel. 18 and beyond are incorporating UAVs with 5G and Beyond 5G (B5G) networks. More specifically, 3GPP Release 17 is focused on enhancing Unmanned Aerial System (UAS) capabilities through connectivity improvements, identification and tracking enhancements, and advancements in application layer support and API frameworks [1]. 3GPP Release 18, known as "5G Advanced", builds upon the aforementioned aspects, with improvements in flight planning, seamless network switching, and UAS tracking capabilities and identifies potential architecture and system level enhancements for 5GS to support additional scenarios and requirements for

UAV and Urban Air Mobility (UAM) [2]. 3GPP Release 19 aims to further enhance network support for UAVs, focusing on predicting and monitoring network conditions, ensuring QoS, facilitating flight path planning, and providing reliable command and control traffic [3].

Nevertheless, beyond these enhancements, trials are essential to validate and understand the real-world performance of 5G and B5G networks in relation to UAVs. Many existing studies on QoS and handover effects in 5G networks heavily rely on simulations [4], [5]. While simulations offer a controlled environment for testing, they may not accurately capture the complexities and dynamic nature of real-world cellular networks. Factors such as network congestion, variations in user behaviour, and unpredictable signal fluctuations are often challenging to replicate accurately in simulations. In a similar vein, there are studies utilising private 5G networks also known as Non-Public Networks (NPN), for experimentation or developing 5G enabled vertical applications through the level of programmability they provide [6]. These research-oriented networks, based on their configuration, can serve as a valuable springboard for research and provide a baseline for further experimentation. Towards this goal, several European 5G experimentation facilities have recently emerged, such as 5GENESIS [7], 6G- SANDBOX [8], SUNRISE-6G [9] offering essential experimentation tools for conducting field trials and performance assessment of various services and verticals serving as a valuable playground for research and experimentation. In this direction and using these 5G experimentation facilities, recent publications explore the amalgamation of UAVs and 5G cellular networks as an auspicious solution for enhancing energy efficiency of UAVs. They demonstrate proof-of-concept implementations of such a 5G-enabled UAV with a softwareised Flight Control System (FCS) component at the edge of the 5G network [10]. Additionally, previous studies present trial results and measurements towards delivering the command and control of a UAV over 5G cellular network [11].

This paper presents new findings from 5G-enabled UAV experiments and field trials conducted over a commercial 5G network. Unlike ground-based tests, these trials were performed at typical UAV flight altitude (15 meters above ground), evaluating QoS and its degradation due to handovers as the UAV followed a specific flight plan. Conducted in an urban setting with a dense radio site deployment, the study offers key insights into QoS performance and handover impacts on 5G-enabled UAVs. These findings support stronger conclusions on handover optimization, with practical recommendations for improving latency, throughput, and reliability in real-world 5G and B5G deployments for UAV missions.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section II provides a background analysis for QoS and handover and how they impact UAVs services. Section III introduces the setup of the 5G infrastructure at the time of the experiments, along with the features and scenario methodology used for the realisation of the field trials, while Section IV presents the conducted field trials along with the

produced. Finally, Section V concludes the paper focusing on and highlighting the analysis of the results.

II. QoS CHALLENGES FOR UAV OPERATIONS IN 5G AND B5G NETWORKS

A. QoS Challenges

Key characteristics affecting handovers in UAVs include velocity, and mobility patterns. Moreover, studies have also demonstrated that the altitude at which UAVs operate, significantly influences the frequency of handovers they experience [12]. For instance, UAVs flying at higher altitudes encounter more frequent handovers compared to terrestrial users. Additionally, the three-dimensional movement of UAVs poses challenges to handover management, as their mobility patterns differ from those of traditional terrestrial users. A drone, functioning as a User Equipment (UE), inherently differs from a terrestrial UE in terms of QoS degradation and the impact of handovers. A key consideration in this context is that UAVs, unlike terrestrial UEs, primarily generate uplink data flows, as they typically generate camera stream data. UAVs often operate on both licensed and unlicensed frequency bands shared with terrestrial UEs, leading to co-channel interference. Their higher transmit power, mobility, and Line-of-Sight (LOS) propagation increase the risk of causing disruptions in communication networks.

To elucidate this rationale, “Fig. 1”, depicts two gNodeBs (gNBs) designated as: gNBa and gNBb. The antennas are inclined downward, directing their primary lobes, where the majority of signal power is concentrated towards the ground so a ground user will remain connected to one of the two cells. UAVs, however, are typically served by the antenna’s side lobes. For instance, a drone at position P1 is served by gNBb, even though it is closer to gNBa. As the drone moves a few metres to P2, it switches to gNBa, and then back to gNBb at P3. This indicates an inherent risk of frequent handovers and ping pong handovers potentially, even over short flight distances. A similar scenario occurs when the drone flies horizontally from P2 to P4. In automated UAV missions using 5G technology, frequent handovers occur as the UAV moves across different 5G cells due to fluctuating signal quality. This presents a challenge, given the UAV’s high mobility, dynamic mission demands, and limited onboard resources, making it difficult to maintain reliable control and navigation. Key metrics like Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) and Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ) drive handover decisions, helping to maintain consistent QoS while minimizing disruptions such as latency, reduced throughput, and packet loss between the UAV and control station.

Fig. 1. Antenna tilting and cell association for a UAV flight

In the context where the emphasis is on coverage rather than bandwidth for C2 operations, utilizing bands such as 700MHz (where gNBs can provide service up to 3km) becomes crucial. It is essential that drones support carrier aggregation across different bands and demonstrate increased resilience with lower thresholds for C2 operations, regardless of their proximity to the base stations. On the other hand, analysing UAV mobility factors as well, such as trajectory patterns and altitude changes are essential for optimising handover performance in 5G cellular networks.

Understanding UAV velocity during different flight stages offers valuable insights for predicting and managing handovers, allowing operators to fine-tune handover parameters. By integrating Native AI technology and leveraging 3GPP APIs, operators can enhance control decisions, facilitating seamless UAV integration into cellular networks and improving overall performance. This holistic approach helps predict optimal waypoint paths, minimizing service interruptions from QoS downgrades or signal quality fluctuations during multiple handovers.

III. EXPERIMENTATION FRAMEWORK AND SETUP

A. Experimentation Design and Methodology

As stated in the previous section, managing and optimizing handovers of a UAV during its flight, as it transitions between different cells, poses a significant challenge. During this transition, there can be variations in signal quality provided by the 5G network. These variations can result in temporary signal loss, degradation in communication quality, or interruptions in data transmission. The challenge lies in ensuring seamless and uninterrupted connectivity throughout the UAV's flight, despite these handovers. In the light of the above, COSMOTE and NCSRDI have carried out field trials and a series of experiments in the framework of 5G!Drones H2020 project[14].

Fig. 2. Multitude of gNBs covering the location of the field trials

Fig. 3. Long and short grids for the flight plan

These trials aimed to validate how UAVs can leverage the commercial 5G network to enhance connectivity services and applications, while also assessing the feasibility of automated flight planning, navigation, and investigating the effect of handovers to better understand network behavior across different cells. The trials were conducted at Egaleo Stadium, where a multitude of base stations with different capabilities and varying traffic loads provided coverage across the broader area as depicted in “Fig. 2”. The field trials were designed to evaluate the performance of UAV flight operations and data transmission reliability under a commercial 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) network (COSMOTE) across different phases. Throughout these trials, the handover process was meticulously evaluated and analysed, with a particular emphasis on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) including signal strength, latency, and throughput, encompassing both download and upload rates, to gauge the QoS capabilities of the network. The experiment’s methodology is organized into a series of sequential steps, which encompass positioning the drone, executing flight missions with predetermined patterns, and gathering data on signal strength, downlink and uplink performance. The detailed steps are as follows:

- 1) The drone is positioned at the start line in one corner of the authorised flight area with sufficient battery for at least 10 min of a flight time.
- 2) After clearing the checklist, the drone starts the execution of the flight with C2 over 5G.
- 3) The drone follows a grid-pattern flight plan, as illustrated in “Fig. 3”, in the left part, maintaining a constant altitude of 15 meters to collect signal strength measurements.
- 4) The drone returns to its start position and lands.
- 5) Above steps (1-4) are repeated with the drone executing a shorter S-pattern flight, as shown in the right part of “Fig. 3”, to gather downlink measurements.
- 6) Above steps (1-4) were repeated with the drone executing the shorter S-pattern flight to collect uplink measurements. These steps ensured systematic data collection so as to evaluate the network’s performance under varying flight conditions.

B. Architecture and Setup

The architecture depicted in “Fig. 4” effectively demonstrates the realization of the aforementioned scenario.

Fig. 4. Reference architecture and setup of the scenario

The Drone DJI M300 RKT provided from Hepta Airborne “Fig. 5”, was equipped with a Samsung S20 smartphone, for collecting measurements, and it was controlled using an onboard computer, utilising Quectel RM500Q-AE modem with 4x Taoglas TG55.8113 antennas to get 5G connectivity, provided by Unmanned Life.

The connectivity of the gNBs was based on fiber optic links steering them to the COSMOTE Core Network (CN) located at Renti, a suburb within the Piraeus regional unit, less than 5 kilometres away from the Egaleo Stadium. To monitor and optimize network performance, the COSMOTools Android application was installed and employed in the Samsung S20 smartphone. The application was configured to gather real-time performance data at one second intervals. Data collection utilized an iperf3 server hosted at COSMOTE’s core data centre. Performance metrics were captured during the process, encompassing latency, User Data Protocol (UDP) downlink bitrate, and UDP uplink bitrate. These metrics were systematically monitored to evaluate and optimize the operational efficiency of the network.

Fig. 5. Drone DJI M300 RKT used during the trials

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

This section delves into the detailed quantitative and qualitative findings of the study, offering a comprehensive interpretation of the experimental outcomes. Through rigorous analysis and visualization, the data provides valuable insights into the performance and behaviour of the commercial 5G network during a UAV flight, where handovers (both inter RAT and inter gNB) occurred. These transitions had a significant impact on QoS, influencing factors such as network reliability, latency, and seamless connectivity, elements that are essential for the success of UAV missions. During the trials, the handovers appeared to occur on an ad-hoc basis, contingent upon specific situational factors, density, traffic demands, and UE measurement heuristics.

Fig. 6. Handovers during flight trajectory at height of 15m

A series of handovers among different gNBs near the stadium is depicted in “Fig. 6,” capturing the UAV’s flight along a defined trajectory at an altitude of 15 meters. This sequence was recorded during a specific experiment within the trials, highlighting the network’s response as the UAV transitioned between cells in the area. As illustrated in “Fig. 7” during the downlink measurements, a handover between base stations (BaseI and BaseE) was observed. This caused an instant drop in the maximum downlink rate from 250 Mbps to 150 Mbps, nonetheless reaching 350 Mbps after a few seconds. As shown in “Fig. 8” a number of handovers occurred during the collection of uplink measurements, and their occurrence could be directly associated with either the spikes in values or the measurement gaps of 30-40 seconds observed in the plot, specifically at 15:34:50, 15:35:20, and 15:37:10, suggest handovers between base stations, leading to temporary drops and interruptions in data collection.

Fig. 7. UDP Downlink bitrate per serving gNB at 15m of flight

Fig. 8. Uplink measurements per serving gNB at 15m height of flight

Fig. 9. Latency per serving gNB at 15m of flight

Fig. 10. Downlink measurements per RAT type (LTE, NR)

“Fig. 9” exhibits few spontaneous Radio Access Technology (RAT) type changes that occurred during the flight. Notably, the lower maximum downlink bitrates observed may be attributed to a change in RAT or a base station handover, followed by subsequent background traffic. The Long-Term Evolution (LTE) data points (blue dots) represent intermittent measurements, due to constraints in data collection frequency or intervals, whereas New Radio (NR) measurements (green line and dots) were recorded more consistently.

Fig. 11. Latency vs RSRP at 15m of flight

Finally, the graph in “Fig. 11” highlights the critical role of RSRP in determining network performance by illustrating how signal strength directly impacts latency. It indicates that the RSRP significantly impacts latency, which in turn impacts the QoS. When the RSRP is very low (e.g., around -90 dBm), the latency is extremely high, exceeding 300 ms. As RSRP improves, latency decreases substantially, showcasing how stronger signal strength enhances overall network performance. Upon analysing the data presented in “Fig. 7”, “Fig. 8” and “Fig. 9” alongside the corresponding values in “Fig. 6” a clear correlation emerges between handover events and the measured performance metrics. This analysis reveals a noticeable relationship between the timing of handover events and specific time intervals, particularly during latency

measurements (13:30-13:40), downlink measurements (14:10-14:20), and uplink measurements (15:30-15:40).

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a comprehensive analysis of field trials conducted on a commercial 5G network, highlighting the unique challenges posed by UAVs and cellular networks, especially focusing on the handovers and high altitude signal degradation affecting the overall QoS. By examining QoS performance metrics, including latency and throughput, the field trials demonstrated a clear correlation between QoS and handover performance. With signal strengths ranging from -100 dBm to -66 dBm, we observed significant variations in measurement scale and range, including spikes and gaps. During this period, several handovers occurred primarily between base stations and sometimes between RAT types (LTE and NR). All in all, these findings underscore the importance of advanced handover strategies in enhancing the deployment of UAVs within cellular networks. These results also validate the feasibility of cellular-connected UAVs, especially with 5G, and offer valuable insights for optimizing the network performance parameters to ensure robust and uninterrupted communication. In exploring these challenges, our future research will focus on performance measurements from an application perspective to provide robust insights into network QoS and the implications of handovers in this context. Additionally, exploring efficient decision-making mechanisms for handover, via the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) will be taken into account. These efforts will take place in a laboratory-scale environment using open-source 5G core deployments, with potential comparisons to simulated environments such as Network Simulator-3.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work presented in this paper is partially supported by i) the 6G-SANDBOX project that has received funding from the SNS JU under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101096328, ii) the ENVELOPE project that has received funding from the SNS JU under the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139048.

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